

Dry Electrodes in Non-invasive Electrophysiology (A Review)

Dr. Anjula C. De Silva

Department of Electronic and Telecommunication Engineering
University of Moratuwa
Sri Lanka

Electrophysiology

- Study of electrical activity in the body
- Fundamental element is the 'neuron'

Non-invasive electrophysiological measurements

- Electrocardiogram (ECG)
- Electroencephalogram (EEG)
- Electromyogram (EMG)
- Electrogastrogram (EGG)
- Electrooculogram (EOG)

Key elements in a electrophysiology recording system

- Electrode-skin interface
- Amplifier configuration

Types of non-invasive electrodes

Gel based wet electrode

Dry surface contact electrode

Cognionics Inc.

G.TEC Medical Engineering GMBH

Florida Research Instruments Inc.

Dry Vs. Wet electrodes

Dry electrodes	Wet electrodes
Ease of use <i>(cleanliness, quick setup, user friendliness and self-application)</i>	Inconvenience and discomfort
Long-term usability	Short-term use <i>(degradation of conductive properties of the gel)</i>
Low signal integrity <i>(Sensitive to motion artifacts)</i>	High signal integrity
High electrode-skin impedance (>100k Ω) <i>(Significant increase in the noise and interference picked up from the environment)</i>	Low electrode-skin impedance (<5k Ω)

Penetrating electrodes

Minimally invasive

S. Yao and Y. Zhu, "Nanomaterial-Enabled Dry Electrodes for Electrophysiological Sensing: A Review," *Jom*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 1145–1155, 2016.

L. S. Hsu, S. W. Tung, C. H. Kuo, and Y. J. Yang, "Developing barbed microtip-based electrode arrays for biopotential measurement," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 12370–12386, 2014.

Non-contact electrodes (capacitive)

S. Yao and Y. Zhu, "Nanomaterial-Enabled Dry Electrodes for Electrophysiological Sensing: A Review," *Jom*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 1145–1155, 2016.

B. Chamadiya, K. Mankodiya, M. Wagner, R. B. Nasreddine, and U. G. Hofmann, "Non-contact, non-obtrusive electrocardiography in clinical environments," *2011 5th Int. Conf. Pervasive Comput. Technol. Healthc. Work.*, no. July 2014, pp. 101–106, 2011.

Semi-dry electrodes

10–20 $\mu\text{L/h}$

Ti/TiN dry electrodes

- Small tip (1.5 mm) to reach the skin through hair
- Spring mounted for comfort
- Homogeneous thin films of TiN were deposited, using a reactive DC magnetron sputtering technique at 1:1 ratio
- Silicone cap to fixate electrodes using a pneumatic-driven mechanisms

Mechanism + Ti/TiN electrode

Ti/TiN dry electrodes *continued...*

- Lowest impedances are visible at the frontal and fronto-temporal electrodes with mean values below 250 k Ω at 500 mbar.

	5 Hz	40 Hz	10k Hz	
Ti/TiN	824 k Ω	213 k Ω	54 k Ω	Capacitive behaviour
Ag/AgCl	17 k Ω	14 k Ω	12 k Ω	Resistive behaviour

Porous Ti semi-dry electrodes

- The electrode is fabricated by porous Ti and Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)
 - Ti – electrode
 - PDMS electrolyte reservoir (200 μl saline)

Porous Ti semi-dry electrodes *continued...*

Average impedance from forearms

Silver nano-wires (AgNW)

- AgNW embedded below the surface of the PDMS matrix
- Maintain a conformal contact with the skin, even under motion
- Outperformed the wet Ag/AgCl electrodes with less motion artifacts

Carbon nanotubes (CNT)

- CNT into adhesive PDMS (aPDMS)
- Serpentine lines as stretchable interconnects
- DRL to reduce the noise

Penetrate electrodes based on CNT

- Multi-walled CNT forest as the penetrating ECG electrode
- Penetration depth of stratum corneum 10–15 μm

Interfacing circuits

- Two types
 - Passive electrodes
 - Active electrodes

Passive electrodes connected to a instrumentation amplifier (IA)

Active electrodes (AE)

Advantages of active electrodes

- Due to in-situ amplification, less impact from noise afterwards
- Can use light weight, low cost cables (no requirement of shielding)
- High input impedance
 - Minimal effect from the impedance due to electrode-skin interface
- Low output impedance
 - Minimal effect from stray capacitance on cables and from cable movements
- Disadvantage
 - More than a single cable required for an electrode

Analog buffer

- High input impedance, low output impedance, and low gain variation
- Can be used for active shielding
- Buffer only requires three wires (V_{dd} , V_{ss} , and V_{out})

Active shielding

DC/AC-coupled amplifier

- In most cases, the important signal is the AC
- But slow cortical potentials (<1 Hz) require DC coupling
 - After effect of the stimulus or expectation of a new stimulus
- DC servo loop
 - V_{out} – AC output
 - V_{fb} – DC output

Flicker Noise reduction and op-amp offset compensation

- Flicker noise ($1/f$) is a dominant low frequency noise
- Op-amp offset is inherent due to non-identical nature of internal components
- Problem – Amplification of these noises will reduce the dynamic range of amplifiers and ADC at later stages
- Solution – chopper circuit

Electrode offset compensation

- A DC servo loop
 - A feedback loop with a low-pass filter (<0.5 Hz)

CMRR enhancement

- Common mode feed-back (CMFB)
 - Also known as 'driven right leg'
 - Common mode voltage is feedback into the body
- Common mode feed-forward (CMFF)
 - Can be integrated into a noninverting amplifier

Fabrication

- 8 channel EEG Active Electrode acquisition system
 - A standard TSMC 0.18 μm CMOS process
 - Area of 17.6 mm^2
 - Power consumption: $48 \mu\text{A}$ from 1.8 V (per channel)
 - 6 wires
- 12 channel EEG Digital Active Electrode
 - A standard TSMC 0.18 μm CMOS process
 - Area of 15.8 mm^2
 - Power consumption: $58 \mu\text{A}$ from 1.8 V (per channel)
 - 5 wires

J. Xu, S. Mitra, A. Matsumoto, S. Patki, C. Van Hoof, K. A. A. Makinwa, and R. F. Yazicioglu, "A Wearable 8-Channel Active-Electrode EEG / ETI Acquisition System for Body Area Networks," vol. 49, no. 9, pp. 2005–2016, 2014.

J. Xu, B. Busze, C. Van Hoof, K. A. A. Makinwa, and R. F. Yazicioglu, "A 15-Channel Digital Active Electrode System for Multi-Parameter Biopotential Measurement," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 50, no. 9, pp. 2090–2100, 2015.

Thank you!